

Finite Element Analysis of Voltage and Electric Field Distribution on High-Voltage Disk Insulators with Contamination Effects

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ABSTRACT

The voltage and electric field distribution within high-voltage insulators is an essential parameter in assuring reliability and performance under various operating conditions. The present paper discusses the finite element analysis (FEA) using MATLAB on a disk insulator for evaluating voltage and electric-field distributions over the surface of insulators. This insulator model based on standard dimensions (height: 153 mm; diameter: 330 mm; minimum creepage distance: 219 mm) was used to analyse various levels of contamination in order to study the effects of rainfall on leakage current. The simulation results elaborate on the probable regions of high stress, partial discharge, and insulation failure. The comparison between the numerical results and theory is to further validate the capability of FEA in predicting electrical performance. This knowledge is instrumental in developing an understanding of insulation behavior, thereby assisting in designing and maintaining high-voltage systems.

KEYWORDS:- Electric Field Distribution, 3D Finite Element Method, Porecelian Disc Insulator, MATLAB, AUTOCAD.

1. INTRODUCTION

As far as electric transmission systems are concerned, the most crucial elements are high-voltage insulators which provide electrical insulation and mechanical strength between conductors and supporting structures. The performance of these systems depends mainly on the voltage and electric field on the insulator's surface. Contamination, harsh environments, or the shape of the insulators can create uneven voltage and electric field distributions, leading to higher stress in certain areas. These zones can experience phenomena like corona discharge, partial discharge, surface tracking, and flashover, which all cause failure of insulation as well as an interruption in services [1], [2].

The factors mentioned above can disrupt electricity services, that is why significant research has been dedicated to studying voltage and electric field distributions on high-voltage insulators over the years. In earlier times, researchers tried to use analytical techniques for example, integral equations methods to examine the effect of an insulator on the performance of thin contamination layers [3]. Numerical methods, such as the boundary element method and charge simulation method, were used to analyse how pollution affects electric field distortion across various insulator shapes and contamination levels [4], [5]. Those techniques were essential because they revealed the importance of surface and material properties in insulator behaviour.

Recently, the finite element method (FEM) has emerged as one of the important versatile tools with good reliability and reasonable accuracy for solving problems of voltage and electric field distributions because of the possibility of handling complex geometries and boundary conditions. A previous study [6] used FEM modeling on polluted insulators with unsymmetrical boundary conditions while another study [7] investigated the performance of ceramic disc insulators with the aid of 2D FEM modeling. Experimental and simulated studies on results corroborated by those of live tests, such as presented in [8], show a great degree of confidence in the theoretical and practical use of FEM in the domain of high-voltage insulator analysis.

A continuation of this line of work studies the finite element analysis of a high-voltage disk insulator, designed in AutoCAD and analysed in MATLAB. This insulator model, based on standard dimensions (height: 153 mm, diameter: 330 mm, and creepage distance: 219 mm), is subjected to field data on contamination experiments (e.g., NaCl and KCl) in order to arrive at a more realistic situation. The effects of contamination are examined by modeling a thin conductive film on the surface of the insulator. The information from the simulation about leakage current helps to assess surface conductivity in different situations. This gives a better understanding of how voltage and electric fields spread along the surface of the insulator, focusing on high-stress areas that are more likely to have problems like partial discharge and flashover.

Contrary to earlier works where idealized conditions and commercially available software were adopted, this study ran a 3D FEM model in MATLAB, which presents a more realistic representation of the insulator geometry and environmental factors. The present work, therefore, intends to evaluate changes in the voltage and electric field distributions on clean and contaminated surfaces in a manner where numerical results are evaluated against theoretical precepts and experimental data to validate the model. Likewise, the research also looks into the effects of contamination on leakage current behaviour that could benefit insulator design and maintenance in practical applications.

The findings from this study enhance the understanding of field distortions initiated by contamination and their influence on insulation performance. This study offers practical insights into the design of more reliable insulators and effective strategies for the mitigation of contamination issues [8]-[10], as it attempts to deal with problems concerning the large variability of surface conductivity and localised intensifications of the fields.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Model Design

The disk insulator was designed in AutoCAD with the following specifications:

- Height: 153 mm
- Diameter: 330 mm
- Creepage Distance: 219 mm

The model was then exported in STL format and imported into MATLAB for further analysis. This design was created with consideration for the typical dimensions and geometric features of high-voltage insulators.

2.2 Finite Element Analysis

The finite element analysis was conducted using MATLAB's PDE toolbox. The following Laplace equation is defined:

$$\nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla V) = 0 \quad (1)$$

sought to solve for the voltage distribution where ϵ is the permittivity and V is the electric potential difference. Electric energy was afterward calculated by the following relationship:

$$E = -\nabla V \quad (2)$$

The Geometry was realized through the adaptive refinement technique. This was done to ensure accurate results in high-stress regions.

2.3 Experimental Data

Leakage current data were collected for different levels of contamination using sodium chloride (NaCl) and potassium chloride (KCl). Six voltage levels—5 kV, 10 kV, 15 kV, 20 kV, 25 kV, and 30 kV—were applied, and the corresponding leakage current was recorded for each contamination level. MATLAB was utilized to preprocess and analyse this data.

3. RESULTS

The finite element analysis (FEA) of the disk insulator offered valuable insights into the voltage distribution across its surface. The voltage distribution displayed a smooth gradient along the insulator. However, contamination effects resulted in a non-uniform potential distribution, leading to localized variations in voltage. Significant voltage drops were noted in areas near the electrode-air interface, indicating potential points of high electric stress.

Figure 1 illustrates the computed voltage contours, showing how the potential gradually decreases from the high-voltage electrode (30 kV) to the grounded end (0 V).

Figure 1 Voltage Distribution on the Insulator

The electric field was calculated based on the voltage gradient, and the results were visualized using MATLAB. The highest intensity of the electric field was observed near the high-voltage electrode and at the edges of the sheds, where the field lines are concentrated. As expected, the electric field

intensity gradually decreased toward the grounded end. Additionally, localized enhancements of the electric field were detected in areas with high surface conductivity, such as contaminated regions, which increased the risk of partial discharge and flashover.

Figure 2 shows the electric field intensity across the insulator surface.

Figure 2 Electric Field Distribution on the Insulator

Integrating experimental data into our simulation enabled us to analyse the impact of contamination on leakage current. Clean insulators displayed a uniform electric field distribution with minimal leakage currents. Moderately contaminated insulators showed increased surface conductivity, which led to localized distortions in the electric field. In contrast, heavily contaminated insulators resulted in excessive leakage currents and high electric field intensities at the edges of the sheds, thereby increasing the probability of flashover.

Table 1: Peak Electric Field Values for Different Contamination Levels

Contamination Type	Peak Electric Field (kV/mm)	Risk of Flashover
Clean Surface	0.9	Low
NaCl Contaminated	1.5	Moderate
KCl Contaminated	1.8	High

Figure 3 demonstrates how varying levels of contamination (NaCl and KCl) altered the distribution of the electric field.

Figure 3 Leakage Current vs Voltage with contaminations

To validate the accuracy of the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) model, the simulated electric field results were compared with theoretical calculations and available experimental data. The findings demonstrated a close agreement, with discrepancies falling within $\pm 5\%$ between the FEA results and theoretical predictions. Additionally, there was a strong correlation with previous experimental studies, which reinforces the numerical model's accuracy. However, minor deviations were observed in cases with significant contamination, likely due to surface roughness effects that were not fully captured by the model.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The finite element analysis (FEA) of the disk insulator offered essential insights into the distribution of voltage and electric fields along its surface. The voltage distribution exhibited a smooth gradient, transitioning from 30 kV at the high-voltage electrode to 0 V at the grounded end, consistent with electrostatic theory. However, localized variations were noted, particularly in areas with surface contamination, which led to intensification of the electric field in certain regions.

The electric field distribution indicated that the highest field intensities were concentrated near the electrode-air interface and the edges of the shed, suggesting potential areas for partial discharge or flashover. In clean conditions, the electric field remained relatively uniform, with a peak intensity of approximately 0.9 kV/mm. However, under contamination from substances like NaCl or KCl deposits, surface conductivity increased, resulting in distortions in the electric field. This change led to higher peak values, ranging from 1.5 kV/mm to 1.8 kV/mm. These high-field regions align with the practical failure points observed in real-world insulator operations.

Contamination significantly affects the surface leakage current, which in turn impacts the electric field distribution. Contaminated areas exhibited stronger field intensities, increasing the likelihood of dielectric breakdown. High surface conductivity facilitated leakage currents, which, under wet or polluted conditions, could lead to complete insulator breakdown. The experimental leakage current data incorporated into the FEA model confirmed that a clean insulator exhibited negligible leakage current and a uniform field distribution. A moderately contaminated insulator (e.g., NaCl deposits) displayed slightly increased leakage currents, leading to moderate field distortions. A heavily contaminated insulator (e.g., KCl deposits) showed significant field distortions and high leakage currents, resulting in a high risk of flashover.

Using the measured leakage current data, an empirical formula for leakage current can be proposed as:

$$I=k\cdot\left(\frac{V}{L}\right)^n \cdot\sigma^\alpha \quad (3)$$

where:

k = Empirical scaling factor (depends on insulator material)

V = Applied voltage (kV)

L= Creepage distance (mm)

σ = Surface conductivity (S/m, dependent on contamination levels)

n, α = Empirical constants from curve fitting

Curve fitting using MATLAB yielded the following best-fit parameters: $k=-10.0019$, $n=1.041$, $\alpha=0.241$. This formula accurately predicted leakage current across different contamination levels (Figure 3).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study thoroughly examined the distribution of voltage and electric field on a high-voltage disk insulator using MATLAB's finite element analysis (FEA). In examining the case, this study made it clear that surface contamination greatly affects electric field intensification as well as the behaviour of leakage current, showing that contaminants like NaCl and KCl severely worsen the electric field distortions and leakage currents and the chances of flashover. The study has proven the numerical model to be in concordance with other theoretical and experimental data by combining experimental leakage current measurements with FEA simulations and achieving the results within the set margins of $\pm 5\%$. Moreover, the results of this study shed more light on the performance of insulators during harsh environmental conditions and why contamination control is necessary to meet reliability targets. Additionally, the empirically derived formula for leakage current becomes a tool for estimating the insulation performance in practical conditions.

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